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IMPACT OF STATIC VAR COMPENSATOR (SVC) DEVICES ON POWER SYSTEM LOSSES

UTJECAJ SVC UREĐAJA NA GUBITKE U MREŽI

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Abstract: The aim of this paper is to investigate the effect of the location of the SVC installation on the amount of power losses in the power system. The IEEE modified system with 3 wind turbines and 24 nodes was used as the test system. For the purpose of discovering the optimal location of the SVC device, GAMS programme was used. Comparing the results for losses before and after setting SVC to the optimum position in order to minimize losses, it was concluded that the position and power of the SVC device greatly influence the amount of losses in the system.

Keywords: SVC, optimal allocation, IEEE 24-test bus system

Sažetak: Cilj ovoga rada je istraživanje utjecaja lokacije postavljanja SVC uređaja na iznos gubitaka snage u elektroenergetskom sistemu. Kao testni sistem korišten je IEEE modifikovani sistem sa 3 vjetroagregata i 24 čvora. U svrhu otkrivanja optimalne lokacije SVC uređaja, korišten je program GAMS. Upoređujući rezultate za gubitke prije i poslije postavljanja SVC-a na optimalno mjesto, u cilju minimizacije gubitaka, došlo se do zaključka da pozicija i snaga SVC uređaja umnogome utječu na iznos gubitaka u sistemu.

Ključne riječi: SVC, optimalna lokacija, IEEE testni sistem sa 24 čvora

INTRODUCTION

Flexible AC transmission systems, so-called FACTS devices, can help reduce power flow on overloaded lines. Therefore, it will result in a decreased loadability of the power system and in fewer transmission line losses. On the other hand, the use of FACTS devices will improve the system stability and security [1].

There are parallel, series and combined FACTS devices. Each of these types of FACTS has its own advantages. If main focus is on optimal power flow (OPF), it is best to use the series FACTS devices. Likewise, if the goal is to achieve the desired voltage levels in EES, then the preferred is the use of the parallel ones. Devices with the best features are certainly combined FACTS devices although they are the most expensive FACTS devices [1]. Static VAR Compensator (SVC) device consists of two components - TSC (Thyristor Switched Capacitor) and TCR (Thyristor Controlled Reactance). The TSC–TCR compensator usually comprises n TSC banks and a single TCR connected in parallel. The rating of the TCR is chosen to be $1/n$ of the total SVC rating. TCR provides continuous control within the reactive-power span of each step, and at the same time the capacitors in TSCs

can be switched in discrete steps. As the size of TCR is small, the harmonic generation is also substantially reduced. The main motivation in developing SVCs was to enhance the operational flexibility of the compensator during large disturbances and to reduce the steady-state losses.

Many recent studies have focused on FACTS devices allocation considering voltage stability and power system losses. In [2] a systematic method in finding optimal location of SVC is proposed to improve voltage profile of a power system under normal conditions and under contingency conditions with Artificial Bee Colony (ABC) Algorithm. In [3] the proposed methodology is based on the evolutionary algorithm known as Evolution Strategies (ES). Simulations are carried out on a modified IEEE 30-bus test system. In order to find suitable FACTS locations more easily and with more flexibility, paper [4] presents a graphical user interface (GUI) based on a genetic algorithm (GA). It was proven able to find the optimal locations and sizing parameters of multitype FACTS devices in large power systems. The paper [5] shows that voltage deviation is considered as a main objective function and it is minimized using different shunt connected FACTS devices like SVC and STATCOM. The mentioned paper uses the Metaheuristic Grey Wolf Optimization (GWO) Algorithm. This algorithm has been used for optimal setting of control variables to minimize the voltage deviation. In [6] a Particle Swarm optimization (PSO) method is presented to deal with reactive power

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dispatch optimization problem. Simulation results on the IEEE 14-bus test system and IEEE 30-bus test system are presented and compared with those of the Genetic Algorithm (GA) and Differential Evolution (DE). In [7], a new technique for the optimal location and design of two kinds of FACTS devices (SVC and TCSC) is proposed handling the minimization of transmission losses in electrical network. Using the proposed scheme, the type, the location and the rating of FACTS devices are optimized simultaneously. On the other hand, in [8], an approach for optimal allocation of flexible AC transmission system (FACTS) devices under deregulated power systems is presented. That paper formulates the overall problem as a mixed integer nonlinear programming problem, solved by using hybrid Particle Swarm Optimization. The effectiveness of the proposed approach is demonstrated on modified IEEE 14-bus test system. In [9] a Genetic Algorithm (GA) for allocation of FACTS devices is presented. Proposed algorithm is tested on IEEE 30-bus power system for optimal allocation of multi-type FACTS devices. In [10], a new multi-objective planning framework, namely the Non-dominated Sorting Improved Harmony Search (NSIHS), is presented. It is able to evaluate the impact of FACTS placement for an enhancement of voltage stability. In [11], Differential Evolution (DE), a population based stochastic meta-heuristic optimization algorithm is applied for optimal placement of static var compensator (SVC) aimed at the voltage security enhancement of a power system. The SVC placement is considered to be a planning problem and is formulated as a multi-criteria problem comprising minimization of real power loss, voltage security and investment cost of SVC under single line outage contingencies. In [12] optimal location of SVC using this hybrid PSO-GA algorithm is found. The optimal location of SVC using GA and PSO algorithm has also been found. In [13], a genetic algorithm attempting to identify the optimal location and size of a SVC is proposed. In the said paper, a multi-criteria function is developed, comprising of both operational objectives and investment costs. The computer programme is run on a 13 nodes test system, assessing improvements in voltage profile and reducing power losses.

In this paper the impact of SVC devices on power losses will be analyzed, observing modified IEEE 24-test bus system. All testing will be performed by using CONOPT solver from GAMS, differently to the literature approaches dominantly based on the usage of heuristic methods.

This paper will be organized in 5 sections. Description of SVC devices and their mathematical models will be given in the first section. The second Section will present the problem formulation. Section 3 is reserved for programme GAMS and the IEEE 24-test network description.

The fourth Section will present the results, obtained in the GAMS, for testing the impact of SVC devices on power losses. Final remarks and conclusion are given in Section 5.

1. SVC DEVICES

FACTS devices play a significant role in controlling the power flows of the power transmission network, the voltage fluctuations and the stability of the system. SVC is a vital member of FACTS family and it is used:

- to maintain the magnitude of bus voltage at the desired level,
- to improve voltage security,
- for damping power oscillations and
- for reactive power compensation etc. of a power system.

The SVC device behaves like a variable reactance connected in shunt that can be regulated as an inductive or capacitive compensation device. The objective of SVC is to inject reactive power to a bus or absorb reactive power from the bus where it is connected in order to regulate voltage magnitude of the bus at the point of connection.

SVC combines a series capacitor bank shunted by thyristor-controlled reactor. Therefore, the SVC can be considered as a synchronous compensator modelled as PV bus, with Q limits designed by its rated size Q_{SVC} . This characteristic can be modelled by a shunt-connected variable susceptance B_{SVC} (Figure 1). As the size of the SVC is limited, a lower and an upper bound of susceptance, B_{SVCmin} and B_{SVCmax} , exist for the effective susceptance B_{SVC} [11]. Thus:

$$B_{SVCmin} \leq B_{SVC} \leq B_{SVCmax} \tag{1}$$

Figure 1: Model of SVC device

Range of shunt susceptance is according to the below:

$$-0.5 \leq B_{SVC} \leq 0.5 p.u. \tag{2}$$

Moreover, the relationship between injected VAR and bus voltage may be described as follows:

$$Q_{SVC} = -V_k^2 B_{SVC} \tag{3}$$

Considering the SVC in transmission line, the active and reactive power flowing between buses i and j is as follow [12]:

$$P_{ij} = V_i^2 G_{ij} - V_i V_j (G_{ij} \cos \delta_{ij} + B_{ij} \sin \delta_{ij}) \quad (4)$$

$$Q_{ij} = -V_i^2 (B_{ij} + B_{SVC}) - V_i V_j (G_{ij} \sin \delta_{ij} - B_{ij} \cos \delta_{ij}) \quad (5)$$

The total active and reactive losses are calculated as:

$$P_{Loss} = \sum P_{ij} + \sum P_{ji} \quad (6)$$

$$Q_{Loss} = \sum Q_{ij} + \sum Q_{ji} \quad (7)$$

The main objective of this paper is to find the optimal location of SVC in such a way that the total power losses of the system are minimized and, at the same time, for the system constraints to be met.

2. PROBLEM FORMULATION

The goal of this paper is to show the influence of SVC devices on the total power loss depending on its location. Simultaneously, solving of the optimal power flow (OPF) problem is handled. The goal of the OPF optimization is to find the most suitable power production of all generators and power flow through the power network. Function that is minimized represents the total power loss.

Optimal function or objective function (OF), is formulated as follows:

$$OF = \sum_{k=1}^n [g_{ij} (V_i^2 + V_j^2 - 2V_i V_j \cos \theta_{ij})] \quad (8)$$

where n is the number of lines of the network; V_i and V_j are the nodal voltages of bus i and bus j respectively; g_{ij} is the conductance of the line ij , and θ_{ij} is the phase angle difference between the busses i and j .

The balance equations of active and reactive power in buses are formulated as follows:

$$P_{bus,t}^g + P_{bus,t}^{LS} + P_{bus,t}^W - P_{bus,t}^L = \sum_{node} P_{bus,node,t} \quad (9)$$

$$Q_{bus,t}^g + Q_{bus,t}^{LS} + Q_{bus,t}^W - Q_{bus,t}^L = \sum_{node} Q_{bus,node,t} \quad (10)$$

where $P_{bus,node,t}$ and $Q_{bus,node,t}$ represent active and reactive power trough branches, respectively. $P_{bus,t}^g$ and $Q_{bus,t}^g$ are active and reactive power generated by thermal unit g at time t , respectively. $P_{bus,t}^w$ and $Q_{bus,t}^w$ are active and re-

active power generated by wind turbine connected to bus bus at time t . $P_{bus,t}^{LS}$ and $Q_{bus,t}^{LS}$ are active and reactive load shedding in bus bus at time t . $P_{bus,t}^L$ and $Q_{bus,t}^L$ are active and reactive load in bus bus , at time t . For the node in which we connect the SVC, (10) will be slightly different. There will be another member on the left side of equation, which is the power of the SVC device Q_{SVC} .

In order to calculate power through branches, we can use the following equation:

$$I_{bus,node,t} = \frac{V_{bus,t} \left| \frac{\delta_{bus,t} - V_{node,t} \left| \frac{\delta_{node,t}}{Z_{bus,node}} \right. + \frac{bV_{bus,t}}{2} \right| \left| \frac{\delta_{bus,t} + \frac{\pi}{2}}{2} \right.}{Z_{bus,node} \left| \theta_{bus,node} \right.} \quad (11)$$

In (11), $I_{bus,node,t}$ represents current trough the branches at time t , in [A]. $V_{bus,t}$ and $V_{node,t}$ are the voltages, in [V], $\delta_{bus,t}$ and $\delta_{node,t}$ are the voltage angels at time t , in [rad], $Z_{bus,node}$ is the impedance of the branch, in [Ω], $\theta_{bus,node}$ is the impedance angle of the branch, in [rad] and b is variable cost in [\$/MW].

Now, the power is calculated by using the following equation:

$$S_{bus,node,t} = V_{bus,t} \left| \frac{\delta_{bus,t}}{Z_{bus,node}} \right. \cdot I_{bus,node,t}^* \quad (12)$$

Active and reactive power is calculated based on apparent power and they are formulated as follows:

$$P_{bus,node,t} = \text{real}\{S_{bus,node,t}\} = \frac{V_{bus,t}^2}{Z_{bus,node}} \cos(\theta_{bus,node}) - \frac{V_{bus,t} \cdot V_{node,t}}{Z_{bus,node}} \cos(\delta_{bus,t} - \delta_{node,t} + \theta_{bus,node}) \quad (13)$$

$$Q_{bus,node,t} = \frac{V_{bus,t}^2}{Z_{bus,node}} \sin(\theta_{bus,node}) - \frac{V_{bus,t} \cdot V_{node,t}}{Z_{bus,node}} \sin(\delta_{bus,t} - \delta_{node,t} + \theta_{bus,node}) - \frac{bV_{bus,t}^2}{2} - \frac{B_{SVC} V_{bus,t}^2}{2} \quad (14)$$

However, any optimization problem has certain limitations. In this case, we need to pay attention to technical limitations like the maximum amount of power that can flow through the grid, minimal and maximal active and reactive power that can make generator units etc.

The thermal units and power lines have their limits. They are given as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} -S_{bus,node}^{\max} &\leq S_{bus,node,t} \leq S_{bus,node}^{\max} \\ P_g^{\min} &\leq P_{g,t} \leq P_g^{\max}, \quad Q_g^{\min} \leq Q_{g,t} \leq Q_g^{\max} \\ P_{g,t} - P_{g,t-1} &\leq RU_g, \quad P_{g,t-1} - P_{g,t} \leq RD_g \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

In (15), S_{maxbus} node is maximum apparent power which can flow through branch in [MVA]. Active and reactive powers are limited with minimum and maximum powers that generating units can produce. As every thermal unit has ramp rates, increasing and decreasing rates are limited with ramp-up (RU_g) and ramp-down (RD_g).

Limitations for load shedding are given as follows:

$$0 \leq P_{bus,t}^{LS} \leq P_{bus,t}^L \quad (16)$$

The power of wind curtailment and the wind power are formulated in (17) and (18), respectively.

$$P_{bus,t}^{wc} = w_{bus,t} \lambda_{bus}^w - P_{bus,t}^w \quad (17)$$

$$0 \leq P_{bus,t}^w \leq w_{bus,t} \lambda_{bus}^w \quad (18)$$

In (17) and (18), $w_{bus,t}$ is availability of wind turbine and λ_{bus}^w is capacity of wind.

3. PROGRAMME GAMS AND IEEE 24-TEST BUS SYSTEM

The results in this paper were obtained using the GAMS programme. The General Algebraic Modelling System (GAMS) is a modelling tool for mathematical programming and optimization purposes. It can be used to solve different types of optimization problems [14].

In this paper, IEEE 24-test bus system is used for test network. Graphical view of this network is given in Figure 2. On the other hand, we observed modified IEEE 24-test bus system (in nodes 8, 19 and 21 we added wind turbines). Wind power availability production in [pu] during 24h is given in Figure 3. Maximal power of generators in nodes is seen at 100 MW, 150 MW and 200 MW in nodes 21, 19 and 8, respectively. Assumed consumption diagram of this network in [pu] during 24h is given in Figure 4.

Figure 3: Wind availability in [pu]

Figure 4: Consumption diagram

Figure 2: IEEE 24-test bus system

4. SIMULATION RESULTS

The calculation was made on a modified IEEE 24-bus test network with 10 generators and 3 wind turbines in the nodes 8, 19 and 21. The calculation was performed for 12 non-generator nodes.

The operation of the SVC device in both inductive and capacitive mode was observed. The range of values for the SVC susceptance was taken from -0.09 [S] to 0.09 [S], according to (2) [11].

Values of susceptance depend on which node the device is plugged into. From Table I it is clear that different values of susceptance give different values of loss. In order to see the impact of SVC devices on the network, an investigation of optimal aggregate engagement was conducted to minimize network losses. In this way, the SVC device was found to be optimally located in the sixth node. In this case the total losses would equal to 0.909 [pu], and would be lower than in the case without SVC device for 0.078 [pu]. All of this provided that the SVCs susceptance be 0.09 [S].

The production of reactive power for two generators, one in node 2, and one in node 18 is shown in Figure 5. Node

2 is the closest to node 6, in which the SVC is coupled, and node 18 is the furthest to node 6. From Figure 5 it can be concluded that the generation of reactive power in node 18 is identical before and after the insertion of the SVC, whereas for node 2 we have a certain difference. This is an expected situation as the voltage, and therefore

indirectly reactive power, is a local parameter. In presentation of results, we also showed the reactive power in node 7, and node 16, where the impact of SVC devices can be seen (see Figure 6). Also, we presented reactive power flow between nodes 6 and 10, and between 6 and 2 (Figure 7).

Table I: Power losses with and without different SVCs

Node	Susceptance						
	-0.09 S	-0.06 S	-0.03 S	0 S	0.03 S	0.06 S	0.09S
20	0.985	0.986	0.986	0.987	0.987	0.988	0.988
10	1.021	1.009	0.998	0.987	0.976	0.965	0.955
6	1.1	1.053	1.017	0.987	0.96	0.934	0.909
12	1.001	0.996	0.991	0.987	0.982	0.978	0.974
11	1	0.995	0.991	0.987	0.983	0.979	0.975
14	0.991	0.989	0.988	0.987	0.986	0.985	0.984
24	0.983	0.984	0.985	0.987	0.988	0.99	0.993
3	0.978	0.98	0.983	0.987	0.991	0.996	1.001
4	0.986	0.986	0.986	0.987	0.988	0.99	0.993
5	1.001	0.995	0.991	0.987	0.983	0.98	0.977
9	0.992	0.99	0.988	0.987	0.985	0.984	0.984
17	0.987	0.987	0.987	0.987	0.987	0.986	0.986

Figure 5: Reactive power in nodes 2 and 18 without SVC

Figure 6: Reactive power generation with and without SVC in nodes 7 and 16

Figure 7: Reactive power generation with and without SVC between nodes 6 and 10, as well as between nodes 6 and 2

5. CONCLUSION

In this paper, programme GAMS has been used to find the optimal placement and sizing of SVC to minimize power system losses. The proposed approach has been implemented on IEEE 24-bus system. The criteria for selection of optimal placement of SVC were to reduce the power losses in the power grid. The simulation results show that an optimal placement of SVC power can significantly reduce losses.

Future work will be focused on the Unified Power Flow Controller (UPFC device), which is the latest combined FACTS device; according to researches, it has been proven to be the one with the best performance. The optimal location for UPFC will be sought in order to minimize power losses and voltage deviation.

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